

CO-OPERAS workshop, Porto, Sept. 17 2019

During the Open Science Fair 2019, CO-OPERAS organized a workshop on

Defining FAIR in the SSH: issues, cultures and practical implementations

<https://www.opensciencefair.eu/workshops-2019/defining-fair-in-the-ssh-issues-cultures-and-practical-implementations>

Summary

FAIR data in SSH

[1st group: FAIR data and discoverability](#)

[2nd group: FAIR and innovation in scholarly communication](#)

A FAIR ecosystem use case for the SSH

1. Summary

Programme

- **What is “FAIR data” in the SSH**
 - FAIR principles in the SSH | 10 min [[Presentation](#)]
 - Focus Groups: | 45 min
 - FAIR Data and discoverability | Moderator: P. Kraker [[Presentation](#)]
 - FAIR and innovation in scholarly communication | Moderator: E. Tóth-Czifra [[Presentation](#)]
- **Building an international FAIR ecosystem in the SSH**
 - Programmatic outline: CO-OPERAS / the new UC Digitalis ecosystem (Coimbra) | 20 min [[Presentation](#)]
 - Discussion | 30 min

Participants

The room was literally full of people (around 80) with different backgrounds (researchers, librarians, IT experts, cultural heritage experts...) representative of the main actors involved.

2. FAIR data in SSH

After a short presentation of the context of the OPERAS project, the CO-OPERAS Implementation Network and the FAIR principles, participants were asked to split into 2 groups.

1st group: FAIR data and discoverability

Moderated by Peter Kraker, OKMaps

Current discovery practices and issues with discovery systems

- How to get an overview of a research field? Reference databases, WoS and Scopus, citation surfing, follow references. Citations are your main indicator.
- Relevant research is recommended by other people.
- As librarians, we need to find the main goal of what they need - fuzzy information need - we don't know what they are looking for. Extreme example: "I want the book with the yellow cover."
- Library systems are set up for known item searches, not exploration.
- Lab studies on research data discovery: fairly common to adjust research question to what data is available. Only using Google to narrow down doesn't work. Sometimes it's better to call someone personally. Some researchers use specific databases, but even for them it is still very hard to find the relevant datasets.
- Different languages, it is hard to understand and not easy to make them widely available, multilingualism features should be implemented.
- Multilingualism: translation currently often done by colleagues

Is Findability (as the F in FAIR is defined) enough?

- Just to be in an index is not enough. Indices need to be available via regular web search, otherwise they cannot be found.
- Humanities issues: create metadata for sculpture, events? Working with historians: interpretation of physical version or digital version. Historians prefer to cite the book as a physical item. Diversity of outputs is not well-represented.
- Physical things can also be reused.
- Journals are moving very fast, books are not moving very fast. Libraries need physical objects to guarantee long-term preservation. If I invest a lot in digital collections - how much will be left for physical collections? Lack of digital skills of users, search, databases. Good readers, not good searchers. Book is very important. This remains unchanged. Study says that this is true for researchers older than 35, but younger researchers prefer e-books.

Requirements for a discovery system for the SSH:

- A lot of content, meta search engine, links to original sources: comprehensiveness.
- Visual search, esp. within the arts.
- Track other expressions: output types.
- Bibliodiversity: many ways of considering a publication. Data in the SSH are the original sources. Combine and test different sources and libraries that are scattered at the moment.
- Minimum amount of usability of the user interface. This is not covered in FAIR - makes data invisible, datasets that could not be found because the interface does not use all of the properties of the data (e.g. translating search terms across domains).
- Keep up with researchers' evolving expectations with regards to discovery

Current training efforts for discovery

- Express sessions on how to search and how to make a databases, monthly
- Longer sessions, twice a year
- First and second semester on exploration of databases
- Catch the people where they are.

- How to find literature, data discovery. Students are most increasingly apt at search, but they are not able to distinguish the quality. Digital literacy programs and policies, esp. for undergraduates. Need to keep doing this at universities. Not only training, but also detect problems when people submit a paper. Be aware of the mechanism from high school, known as “copy-pasta”. Information literacy training.
- But there is a great diversity over the disciplines - for data discovery is also diverse. Difficult to understand how to do it correctly.
- Created Research Data Management course for students. Comprehensive and cross-disciplinary. They did not know that they were producing data.
- FOSTER Plus course on Data Management.

2nd group: FAIR and innovation in scholarly communication

Moderated by E. Tóth-Czifra, DARIAH

See the session outline here: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1024PY7vLTtmpdS8kgsuWadoD0o8wTQFJUC9FSa5Y8/edit?usp=sharing>

Slides: <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/19-F8TkBNBiqSOqE-vXHp89-7ZEGG0N04/edit#slide=id.p1>

Resource list:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/13UY2zgNqqvtArtEy5JVQshhSc8NX0wA5/edit#heading=h.gjdgxs>

We started the session with a brief round of introduction with a focus on how each attendee (mostly librarians, research managers and a few representative from publishers, even less from full-time researchers) contributes to a FAIRer SSH scholarly ecosystem. As a second exercise, we explored together what does FAIR mean in the context of scholarly communication in the SSH and where our problems lie. Below you can see a selection from our answers.

FAIRification challenges in SSH scholarly communication. IPR issues are clearly leading the front.

The answers reflect the diversity of the challenges for FAIR principles application in the SSH area but also more in general:

Technical challenges

- Data is not always findable, nor are the repositories.
- DOIs are still missing
- how to find and reuse small and not international data (specific languages, regions, cities)
- sharing, accessing, discovering non digital data
- ignorance of FAIR principles

Cultural challenges

- define assessment criteria that takes into account specificities of SSH research
- OA journals are not broadly accepted
- prevalence of print culture
- researchers don't "recognize" data in their field
- metrics come from STEM
- rhythm of research
- prevalence of monographs
- no tradition for openly share data
- fear of being scooped by colleagues (competition environment)

Legal challenges

- Embargos on data
- GDPR issues
- copyright issues when sharing and opening the resources
- licenses in the SSH (images and text owned by third parties, eg art history)

As we can see from this quick survey, some challenges are typical of the digital long tail, others are directly related to SSH specificities (third party content, monographs, physical primary data).

In the second half of the session, we formed three groups to discuss the following FAIR scholarly communication use cases:

1. A scholar who is struggling to communicate research results in ways that aligns with their increasingly digital research workflows

2. A small Hungarian language OA Humanities journal/ book publisher is having visibility problems and looking for tools and good practices for upscaling their workflow

4. A subject librarian in arts and humanities is approached by a historian scholar with the following problem: she selected a high-prestige OA journal to publish their project results but it charges 1500 CHF publication fee which is more than her annual budget for such expenses.

(See their presentation in the slides shared)

One general conclusion of all three cases studies where that in many cases, the available infrastructure and the communities who could build on and benefit from them are not well-connected with each other. In other words, the challenges in 'connecting crowds and clouds' became apparent. This is clearly manifested in small humanities journal who do not take advantage of available open infrastructure such as PKP-OJS and are not aware of low-budget solutions for getting PIDs for their outputs or arts and humanities researchers who don't have established mechanisms for data/preprint sharing and in many cases are not aware of their choices and infrastructure available. However, the early-adoption of best data sharing practices within the arts and humanities communities was also reflected in the fact that participants had a lot of suggestions to share even among each other. To keep track of these suggestions, we set up a [resource list](#) that is still open for contributions and commenting.

3. A FAIR ecosystem use case for the SSH

Delfim Leão and Ana Miguéis presented the new UC Digitalis ecosystem for Univ. of Coimbra. UC digitalis represents a typical use case of FAIRification through the creation of an interoperability framework. The final aim is to allow for aggregated search across many disciplines and many types of resources. The creation of the interoperability framework rely on FAIR principles: persistent identifiers, discovery metadata, trusted repositories, clear usage licenses. The first objective is to ensure a smooth migration process from OJS/OMP to the Journals and Books repositories. The second objective is to integrate into this framework other types of data, especially cultural heritage data. In this prospect, the Univ. of Coimbra team presented Alma Mater (<https://am.uc.pt/>), the interface for searching through heritage collections.

The UC Digitalis project directly connects with CO-OPERAS mission by taking into account the organizational, historical and methodologic specificities of the SSH environment. It also shows that the FAIR principles, although providing a useful set of recommendations to

define and manage the data, do require additional work for the design and the set-up of the service effectively providing them.